
HATE CRIMES: AN ARGUMENT FOR ALTERNATIVE PENAL POLICY

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ABSTRACT

Hate crime is understood as manifestation of prejudice based on religious, caste, ethnic, gender or regional identities. Such crimes, apart from being violent in nature, poses threat to the core values of a given society. The hate motivated offender does not only confront with the rule of law but also, essentially, challenges the very existence of his victim. It is this characteristic of hate crime, which makes it barbaric and gruesome.

Societies, having diverse demographic structure, vis., multi-religious, multilingual, and cultural pluralism, are prone to violence based on prejudice and hatred. World history is full of such incidents, and India is no exception. However, until recent cases of ‘mob lynching’, the expression hate crime, per se, was little known to criminal justice system of India. With pronouncing measures for controlling mob-lynching, the Supreme Court of India, brought the ‘hate crime’ on the centre-stage in crime control discourse. A close look of these directives would suggest, firstly, that law enforcement agencies should always be immune from political influence, and secondly, that the problem of mob-violence needs to be addressed in the given socio-political contexts.

The present work intends to examine the expression ‘mob lynching’ from the standpoint of ‘hate crime’ and would try to provide criminological perspective thereof. It will further provide an explanation from established jurisprudential development and will argue for differential treatment in terms of crime control, penal policy and monitoring mechanism. Part-I of the work outlines the growing incidents of hate crime in India. Part-II has examined the definitional conundrum with respect to hate crimes. Part-III of the work briefly outlines the criminology of mob lynching with reference to culpability factors in hate crime. Part-IV of the work examines Hate Crimes under the present legal regime. Part-V concludes with an argument for alternative penal policy including enhance punishment and federal monitoring agency.

KEY WORDS

Hate Crimes; Mob-Violence, Mob-Lynching

I: INTRODUCTION

In the recent past, hate crimes, especially the ‘mob-violence’ and ‘mob lynching’ spilled onto the streets. These incidents of mob violence hit many, causing physical injuries, horrendous assault including death of unarmed men, young and old equally. Zoya Hasan narrated (2017) narrated the trauma of victims of these offences, and how the same percolated so deep that these victims started migrating away from the hate crime prone areas and started settling elsewhere in the country. Erstwhile

political speeches with taste of hatred are being replaced now with unregulated social media, with full of bigotry and hate speeches. Hatred based on religion, caste, race, and place of birth are being advocated through electronic and social media. Hatemongers are using electronic media, social media including WhatsApp, Telegram, Instagram etc. to disseminate hatred. The age-old social solidarity is slowly replaced with hate, suspicion, anger, revenge, and retaliation. Thus, the vicious social atmosphere of hate is busting the social bonding amongst the fellow

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communities. Pushed with the socio-religious beliefs, the law enforcement agencies are also failing miserably in dealing with these hatemongers. State agencies, either end up in absolute denial or limit themselves to a mere criticism and blame-game. The act of lynching is often termed as 'ordinary offence' resultant of usual failure of law and order. In certain cases, even law enforcement agencies were allegedly found taking side of the perpetrators.

However, fortunately enough, the Supreme Court of India took the cognizance of the unabated horrific lynching attacks going unabated in certain parts of the country in the *Tehseen S. Poonawalla v. Union of India*, (Writ Petition (Civil) No. 754 of 2016) and directed the central as well as all the state governments to frame policy/legislation in this regard. The Bench speaking through the then Chief Justice of India, narrated the very purpose and goal of law, and categorically said underlined the "*primary goal of law is to have an orderly society where the citizenry dreams for change and progress is realized and the individual aspiration finds space for expression of his/her potential. In such an atmosphere while every citizen is entitled to enjoy the rights and interest bestowed under the constitutional and statutory law, he is also obligated to remain obeisant to the command of law.*" The observation clearly setting out the scope and the object of 'rule of law' in term 'orderly society', "*citizenry dreams for change and progress*", and above all, the entitlement of each citizen, irrespective of his religion, caste, gender or place of birth, '*to enjoy his and interest bestowed under the constitution*'. While sending a categorical message to the state, reprimanding their *continuous mood of denial* as to the unabated horrendous mob-lynching, , the Apex Court re-assured the ordinary citizen that '*no victim shall go unheard*' and '*no offender will go unpunished*'. Outlining the assurance, the Apex Court stated that "*hate crimes as a product of intolerance, ideological dominance and prejudice ought not to be tolerated; lest it results in a reign of*

terror. Extra judicial elements and non-State actors cannot be allowed to take the place of law or the law enforcing agency."

Regrettably, the message, though being loud and clear, coming directly from the Apex Court of India either failed to hit the eardrum of policy framers or even if it reached there, has not been decrypted properly. On each day, with new incident of mob lynching, new propaganda theories are being pressed into service by various media forums and champions of social media to justify the vulnerability of victims on the line of religious, caste and other identities.

Upsurge in in Hate Crimes

According to a report published (Rawat, 2019), in the year 2016-17 the National Human Right Commission registered one hundred and seventeen (117) cases of alleged victimisation and harassment of members of the minority community. With respect to harassment of Dalits, there was phenomenal increase of 33% in number of cases registered by NHRC. Thus, for the year 2016-17, NHRC registered 505 cases, whereas by 2018-19 this figure increased to 672. Between 2016 and 2019 (till June 15), NHRC registered 2,008 cases where minorities/Dalits were harassed.

In view of the data so recorded, certain fundamental questions are required to be examined empirically. These are those questions which will have direct impact on criminal justice system. To begin with, do we really need to see hate crime differently than any other ordinary crime? If so, what could be the basis thereof? Can a offender be punished differently because he possess different perceived character about the victim? Further, what could be reasons behind lackadaisical response of the state against hate crimes? Why the argument for stringent policy against hate crime is still looking illusionary? Does existing legal framework provides any solution to unabated menace of hate violence? These questions require in-depth deliberation and empiricism.

Methodology

In view of prevalent hate crimes, especially the recent incidents of mob lynching, this work is an attempt to examine the existing definitions of hate crimes in context of India. With the help of jurisprudence developed by various authors, it further delves into the criminology of mob lynching. Finally, by presenting a critical look into the Supreme Court's guidelines dealing with hate crimes, the author presents an alternative system to tackle hate crimes. Thus, the work is primarily doctrinal in nature. The work examines the expression 'mob lynching' from the standpoint of 'hate crime' and would try to provide criminological perspective thereof. It will further provide an argument for differential treatment in terms of crime control, penal policy and monitoring mechanism.

II: THE DEBATE ON DEFINITION

In India, the strangest thing about the hate crime and its concomitants like mob-lynching, is the very denial of its existence by the state. The denial is based on the premise that hate crimes, specially mob-lynching is '*unknown to Indian culture*' as the Indian society is known for its pluralistic existence since long. Constructing further argument from this premise, the state agencies dealing with law and order refer hate crimes similar to that of ordinary crimes, and thus refuse to recognise the distinct nature and characteristics of mob-violence.

For all academic purposes, the word lynching is said to have its origin in the United States of America in the 18th century. Charles Lynch, a Virginia planter, politician, and American revolutionary created and headed an irregular court in Virginia to punish Loyalist supporters of the British during the American Revolutionary War. The terms 'lynching' is believed to be derived from his name. Without going much into the etymology of 'lynching', it is the very phenomena of lynching, which need to be explored and examined. Harsh Mander (2019) suggests that that these words

may have its foreign origin, but the trends of hate crimes and mob violence are not alien to India. Historian Romila Thapar (2018) has provides vivid detail of these violence in her seminal work. Killing of women by branded them as 'witches', violence against Dalits, transgender, religious or sectarian minorities are not unknow to Indian history.

Hate Crime: Definitional Concerns

Generally, the hate crimes connote an idea of violence propelled by hatred against the victim's perceived distinctive character such as religion, race, colour, caste, gender or place or origin. Heidi Hurd and Michael Moor (2004) defines hate crimes as "*criminal manifestation of prejudice.*" They argue for differential treatment of offender in terms of punishment. Professor Heidi's argument (2001) is based on premise that "*hate crimes reflect significantly greater culpability on the part of their perpetrators*", worse than premeditated murders, and thus "*hatred and bias constitute uniquely culpable mental states that merit increased punishment*".

Phyllis B. Gerstenfeld (2004) defines hate crime as a "*criminal act motivated by the victim's personal characteristics, such as race, national origin or religion*". Similarly, C. Petrosino (2003) suggest that hate crime is nothing but '*victimisation of minorities due to their racial or ethnic identities by the member of majority.*' Other thinkers who contributed to the area of hate crime jurisprudence are Anthony M. Dillof (1997) Mohamad (2010), James B. Jacobs and Kimberly Potter (1998), Frederick M. Lawrence (1994), and Barbara Perry (2003). These authors have discussed the normative rules required to punish the hate offender. Their argument ranges from moral conflicts in punishing one's belief to that political limitations.

One of the major problems with respect to hate crime is about distinguishing it with other form of crimes and grading it within various forms of hate crimes. For example, could it be said that hate crime based on religious hatred

is different from hate crimes committed out of caste, colour, gender, or place of birth? If the answer to this question is negative, how the criminal law, specially the penal policy, should rationalises it in terms of sentencing? What if a victim of hate crimes possesses overlapping identities such as religious identity or caste identity along with gender or place of birth? It would be difficult for penal law to attribute distinctive hate motivation in overlapping identities. It may be noted here that hate crimes and related prejudice is not a single act. It is rather an ongoing process in which the victim is victimised every day on regular basis. The continued targeted hostility against the victim make the hate crime altogether different than ordinary crime.

Since hate crimes takes into consideration the belief of the offender about the victim's perceived identity, the debate on definition of hate crimes revolves questing the legitimacy and limits of criminal law in punishing once's belief. In other words, can criminal law punish the offender differently for having distinct belief about victim' identity?

The criminal law requires twin criteria for penalising any act vis., *actus reus* and *mens rea*. Whenever the offender commits a wrongdoing, his *blameworthy state of mind* along with the ensuing of *forbidden consequence* from his act determines his criminal liability. Further, the quantum of sentence, prescribed by the legislation, which is further subject to judicial discretion to bring the proportionality in sentencing, prepares the ground for deciding the punishment. Theorist (Hurd, Heidi M., and Moore, Michael S., 2004) supporting distinct legislation for hate crimes offender argue that the present penal policy, having no place for considering the extra factor of 'hate or prejudice', is inadequate to address the hate crimes. In this regard they count factors based on *greater wrongdoing thesis*, *expressive theory of punishment*, *culpability thesis*, and the *equality thesis*. According to the '*greater wrongdoing thesis*', an offender motivated by hate crime harms

not only its immediate victim, but also causes greater injury to the victim's community. Through his act, he would be sending a message to the entire community of the victim about its being vulnerable, prone to violence and subjected to secondary status. The '*expressive theory of punishment*', taking clue from '*greater wrongdoing thesis*' argue for enhanced punishment as a tool for expressing society's commitment against prejudice. The '*culpability thesis*' examines the very 'blameworthy state of mind' and argues that offender motivated by hate is more blameworthy than offenders who commit ordinary crimes. The necessary element of *mens rea*, though equally required under traditional crimes, the element of 'hate' or 'prejudice' brings hate crimes to a quite different level. *Lastly*, the *equality thesis* prepares ground for arguing that special legislation along with enhanced punishment for hate crime would be necessary to provide equal protection of laws, and thus would bring equality amongst classes, caste or sects. Hate crime laws would be means of evenly distributing the "state-produced good".

However, as stated earlier, the debate around the definition is more about punishing the offender for his 'mere belief'. Individual should be punished only when he causes a forbidden consequence while having specific blameworthy state of mind. Opponent of hate crime legislation argue that 'how can criminal law punish a person for having moral judgement about one's identity. The author submits that the heart of debate is not about one's moral judgement as to victim's identity. It is, rather about the very existence of victim or his community. Any threat to existence of victim or the victim's community is not merely a threat to victim or her community but rather threat to rule of law and the constitutional order. The observation of Supreme Court in *Tehseen S. Poonawalla (supra)* case that "*hate crimes as a product of intolerance, ideological dominance and prejudice ought not to be tolerated; lest it results in a reign of terror*"

is reflection of the same. It is this sense; an argument is advanced hereby for enhanced punishment.

Enhanced Punishment theory and Indian Penal Code

A close reading of Indian Penal Code 1860 would suggest that the idea of *greater wrongdoing, culpability thesis* or *expressive theory* is very much part of the Indian Penal Code, 1860, hereinafter referred as IPC. The relationship between punishment and culpability under Section 299 read with 300 of IPC for same *actus reus* is true reflection of culpability thesis. The *greater wrongdoing thesis* could be explained in terms of Section 153A, 153B etc. of IPC. The '*expressive theory of punishment*' is may be placed to explain minimum punishment for offences like dowry death under Section 304-B IPC, or Offence of Rape under 367, 376A, 376C, 367D, 376E, 367AB, 367DA, and 376DB of IPC. As against general practice providing discretion to the court in terms of punishment, these provisions contain minimum as well as maximum punishment, and these provisions are 'the expression disapproval towards certain kind of offence', and thus sentenced differently.

III: CRIMINOLOGY OF MOB LYNCHING

Mob-violence has been subject matter of study in the field of Criminology and Criminal Psychology. Professor Gustave Le Bon, in his book, '*The Crowd – A Study of the Popular Mind*' (1896), said underline the basic cannons of mob violence. He narrated that once an individual becomes part of crowd, he becomes devoid of his own individuality. After becoming the part of the crowd offender loses touch with personal life, occupation, character, or intelligence. He is '*transformed into a crowd*' with a '*collective mind*' compelling him to feel, think, and act in a manner quite different from what he could have felt in isolation. Thus, as argued by Michael Welner (2017), the Crowd

participation extinguishes one's normal psychological capacities. It is because of this reason that crowd reflects different behaviour than the people who have joined the crowd. Further, in reference to the objective of crowd, it is not at all necessary that same may be the objective of everyone joining the crowds. In reference to hate crime, especially during mob violence, it may absolutely be the case that an individual, suddenly propelled by his hate motivation, may join the crowd, cause horrendous act of violence against the victim. Some of the violent mob crimes may see the involvement of ordinary individual, perpetrated by group of people to commit hate crimes.

Hatred and Prejudice: The Glue that Makes Crowd Work in Consortium

With respect to mob violence, is it necessary to have specific demography or the structure of the crowd? In this regard when a religious violence is committed by a mob, it is often seen that the crowd is drawn from one single religion. However, with respect to caste violence, the demography of mob reflects altogether different feature. Here, the past incidents suggest that different caste groups come together in a spur-of-moment and become hostile victim. What is the reason that these individuals come together and form crowd, even though they have diverse socio-economic status, sometimes even contradictory? Dr Wendy James, in his work '*the Psychology of Mob Mentality and Violence*' narrates three psychological theories i.e. the *Convergence Theory*, *Contagion Theory*, and the *Emergent-Norm Theory* through which he attempts to address crowd behaviour.

As per the Convergence theory the violent behaviour of a crowd is separate to its constituent i.e. the people who are forming the part of the crowd. The crowd reflect the behaviour which is dominant in the people joining it. Thus, it is not crowd which encourages violence, but the people who join it who instigate and engage in violence. The

Contagion theory connects the link between initiation of violence and the continuation thereof. The *Contagion Theory* suggests once the violence is irrupted, the crowd influences each of its constituents in a hypnotic manner. With this hypnotic influence, each member of the crowd behaves in much irrational and emotionally charged manner. In other words, it is the inherent characteristics of a crowd that it makes the individual joining it as [crowd] frenzy. *The Emergent-Norm Theory* combines the two above theories and suggests that mob violence occur because mob would have liked-minded individuals with full prejudice and hatred against the victim and having sense of anonymity leads to violent crowd behaviour.

Dr. Wendy James, though suggest psychology of mob mentality, however, these theories fall short of explaining the glue that makes people work in consort. With experience day today incidents, the author believes that it is the persistent feeling of hatred and prejudice which works as *glue* whereby the individuals having distinct age, economic status, education or profession, after joining crowd behaves in one single direction. The indoctrination done through social interaction contribute a lot in this process.

Professor G.S. Bajpai, (2019) while discussing the '*criminology of mob lynching*' says that mob lynching '*is a typical form of a behavioural manifestation triggered at the instance of a combination of factors.*' Prof. Bajpai proposes certain propositions whereby the criminal behaviour of lyncher could be understood. Professor Bajpai negates the contention that lyncher are always sociopaths or a psychopath. A lyncher is the same youth who grew up, seeing violence as the response and solution of a problem in many situations. He internalises violence as a reality which manifests whenever the occasion arises. Whenever individual joins the crowd, his individual identities melt in, and he represent the collective identity of the crowd. Thus, while committing mob violence,

the conscious, rational mind of the individual is controlled by the unconscious, irrational mind of the crowd. Prof. Bajpai attribute mob lynching to de-individualisation i.e. in case of mob violence, individuals are no longer guided by a sense of personal moral restraint. Thus, the mob so formed, shall be devoid of individual moral restraints, and would reflect the "*extraordinary violent character of each member of the crowd, their ridiculous pride, their sickly susceptibility, the surprising sense of irresponsibility which originates from the illusion of being all-powerful.*" Prof. Bajpai argues that any "*law, to be effective, would require as to how it takes care of dealing with those factors which are the product of human instinct and behaviour.*" It is humbly submitted that criminal law alone would fail to address the mob violence unless the indoctrination done at various level is taken care by state.

IV. HATE CRIME: THE LEGAL REGIME

There are provisions under IPC to deal with the mob violence. Apart from general provisions dealing with *unlawful assembly, riots* and *affray*, IPC prescribes special provisions to punish violence based on hate crimes. Section 153A of IPC penalises acts inter group enmity on ground of religion, race, place of birth, residence, language, etc., Similarly, section 153-B punishes act of making or publishing any imputation or assertion which is prejudicial to national integration. Section 295 of IPC prohibits injuring or defiling any place of worship so as not to insult the religion of any class. Section 295A IPC restricts all the deliberate and malicious acts, which intend to outrage the religious feelings of any class. Section 296 IPC provides punishment to those who voluntarily causes disturbance to any lawfully assembled religious assembly. Section 297 of IIPC prohibits trespassing on burial grounds so that any religious sentiments may not be hurt. Section 298 prohibits uttering words with deliberate intention to wound religious feelings. To protect people who belong to

a class, which suffers with civil disability, 'Untouchability', law has been laid under the Protection of Civil Rights Act, 1955.

Why Lynching is more than Murder?

Opponents of special legislation for hate crimes often argue that demand for special legislation tackling hate crime is essentially political in nature. They would substantiate their argument that even the highest form of hate crimes i.e. lynching is nothing but murder under Indian Penal Code, 1860, and thus can suitably be prosecuted accordingly. The argument, it is submitted, is oversimplification of the facts. Since the hate crimes originate all together differently, than any other crimes, the whole penal policy, effective for traditional crimes, would fail even to initiate the very prosecution of hate perpetrator. The argument is substantiated by the very fact of low conviction rate in communal/caste violence. According to data released by Ministry of Home Affairs, the conviction rate under SC/ST (Prevention of Atrocities) Act is only 16.3% as against the national average of 29.4%. It was this reason that Ministry of Home issued advisory to all states to specially investigate the cases relating to SC/ST.

These provisions were devoid of effective impact on the growing hate crimes and mob violence. In view this, the Communal Violence Bill 2005, was proposed. The provisions of this bill were very stringent in nature and it had proposed enhanced punishment of religious violence/ riots. However, the law proposed failed to get adequate support on the floor of house. It was again revised in the year 2012, but lapse.

Alternative Legal Regime

After a series of lynching at various places, the Supreme Court of India took cognizance of hate crimes, and while denouncing such acts as '*a product of intolerance, ideological dominance and prejudice*' directed the state to prepare comprehensive policy in this

regard. Supreme Court condemned the unabated incidents of lynching as "*an affront to the rule of law and to the exalted values of the Constitution*". (*Tahseen Poonawalla, supra.* para 18). These words of apex court are not of mere cosmetic values. There is a greater need to understand that constitutional virtues are different from majoritarian belief, and to uphold the values enshrined in constitution, a multipronged strategy is required to be observed. This will include *firstly*, special legislation recognising the mob violence and providing effective penal policy with enhanced punishment; *secondly* an alternative centralised mechanism to monitor and guide anti-hate crime strategy.

Demand for Special Legislation

Supreme Court in *Krishnamoorthy v. Sivakumar*, [(2015) 3 SCC 467] stated that "*the law is the mightiest sovereign in a civilized society...No individual in his own capacity or as a part of a group, which within no time assumes the character of a mob, can take law into his/their hands and deal with a person treating him as guilty.*" Terming the mob-lynching as '*the horrendous acts of mobocracy*', Supreme Court recommended the Parliament "*to create a separate offence for lynching and provide adequate punishment for the same.*" Underlining the urgency to ensure effective law and order, maintaining peace and to preserve quintessential secular ethos, pluralistic social fabric, Supreme Court directed the states "*to act positively and responsibly*". These words of apex court are not of mere cosmetic values. The Court, sensing the gravity of scenario, gave measures to be executed within 4 weeks of the judgment. These measures include preventive, remedial and punitive.

The preventive measures suggested by the court are to designate a senior police officer of the state, not below the rank of Superintendent of Police as Nodal Officer in each district. The Nodal Officer shall be responsible for taking measures to prevent

incidents of mob violence and lynching. The Nodal Officer shall also hold regular meetings with the local intelligence and in charge of each police station to identify the existence of the tendencies of mob violence. The Nodal Officer shall make efforts to eradicate hostile environment against any community or caste etc. and shall have regular check on social media to see instances of dissemination of offensive material. The Nodal Officers shall be coordinating the District to with that of the DGP for any inter-district co-ordination. At state level, a special task force would be constituted to procure intelligence reports about hate crimes. Similar coordination is directed to be there between central and state government. Even though the *law and order* are state subject under the Constitutional scheme, the Central Government is directed to issue necessary directions to all the state with a view to regulate serious incidence of hate crime.

Providing remedial measures, the Apex Court directed that all incidents of lynching or mob violence must result into registration of First Information Report. The investigation of hate crimes shall be monitored by the Nodal Officer. While conducting the investigation rights of victims should be taken care. Further, the State Governments shall prepare a lynching/mob violence victim compensation scheme in the light of the provisions of Section 357A of CrPC. The compensation scheme so designed must make necessary provisions for interim relief to be paid within a period of thirty days of the incident. State are being directed to establish special courts for the trial of lynching cases. Some other directions were also given as to witness protection, free legal aid, awarding the maximum punishment prescribed under the law, unless some special situation exist.

Departing from general practice, Supreme Court issued some punitive measures, and directed that non-compliance with the aforesaid directions, shall be considered as an act of deliberate negligence on the part of the officer concern. Reiterating the law laid down

in *Arumugam Servai v. State of Tamil Nadu*, [(2011) 6 SCC 405] court said that the states are directed to take necessary disciplinary action against erring officials.

V. ARGUMENT FOR ENHANCE PUNISHMENT AND FEDERAL MONITORING AGENCY

It is worth repeated here that to solve a problem, the first stage is to recognise its existence. The observation of Supreme Court about hate crime, hate speech and mob lynching is the first step towards penalising the hate crime. The measures suggested by the Court categorically outlines the vision for a comprehensive penal policy in this regard. It recognises the core issues involved, and at same time provides some course correction. *Firstly*, the Court calls for recognising the existence of hate crimes, mob-violence, and mob-lynching. *Secondly*, it talks about speedy trial, protection to witnesses, compensation to the victims of hate crimes and sterns punishment for the offenders. *Thirdly*, court also felt the need for alternative, effective and coordinated policing, right from district level to that of ministry of Home affairs, Government of India for greater crime control.

Argument for Enhance Punishment

As directed by Supreme Court, and argued earlier, criminal justice system needs to evolve the policy of enhanced punishment for hate crimes. The *expressive theory of punishment* would demand that by enhanced punishment, twin message will be send simultaneously. The message will to all future offender that a crime committed out of prejudice or hate will be dealt sternly, and at the same time message will also be send to the victim or the victim's community that state will afford protection to all, and no one should ever feel dejected in the constitution order.

Federal Monitoring Agency

This may be extremely ambitious argument, but hate crime, which is threatening the core

of pluralistic ethos, diminishing the rule of law, and eroding constitutional values need to be tackled differently. The hate crime is required to be dealt with iron hand. In this regard, having a Federal Hate Crime Monitoring Agency could serve the purpose. The idea of having this body for a greater coordination is very much enshrined in the directives of Supreme Court itself. Apart from having inter-state coordination, this agency can preserve the data and sensitive information as to hate crimes. This can work in the line of principle of cooperative federalism and will essentially sub-serve the constitutional objectives. Having centralised bureaucracy for civil administration as well as policing, functioning of such a mechanism will not be much problematic.

SUMMING UP

Going by the direction issued by Supreme Court, many states came up with draft legislation to deal with mob lynching. The draft legislation prepared by UP Law Commission seems to have dealt with the problem stringently. The UP-draft legislation proposes for enhance punishment to lynchers along with punishment of three years on

erring police officials. (Bajpai, 2019). The Manipur government also came up with its Bill against lynching in 2018, incorporating some of these measures. The proposed law provides protection to the victim of mob violence and witness protection including schemes for rehabilitation of victims. The Rajasthan and West Bengal government came up with bill against mob lynching in the year 2019. However, all these provisions are nothing less than half-hearted attempt to deal with hate crime. Parliament of India is also contemplating to have a comprehensive law on this issue. In the meanwhile, the lynching instances continue to rise.

M. K. Gandhi, the father of the nation, has once said that “[he] *object to violence because when it appears to do good, the good is only temporary; the evil it does is permanent...*” to save the nation from a permanent scar, a stringent, well-crafted, futuristic penal policy is required urgently. A policy of zero-tolerance towards hate crime and mob lynching needs to be placed before the law enforcement agency. Unless, an action is taken, in the true sense and spirit of judicial guideline, author afraid that the judicial law making may lose its sanctity.

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